

THE EFFECTS OF BENEFICIAL BACTERIA APPLICATIONS ON YIELD AND QUALITY CHARACTERISTICS OF "CHANDLER" WALNUT VARIETY

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ABSTRACT. In this study, it was aimed to determine the effects of beneficial bacteria treatments on fruit characteristics, yield and shoot length of "Chandler" walnut variety in Saruhanlı district of Manisa province. For this purpose, preparations containing single (*Bacillus subtilis*) and combined (*Pantoea agglomerans*, *Paenibacillus polymyxa*, *Bacillus megaterium*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*) bacteria were sprayed to the trees in two different dates. Accordingly, it was found out that bacterial treatments were more effective than the control group in terms of nut and kernel weight, shell thickness, shrinkage ratio, shoot length and yield. In the single treatment containing *Bacillus subtilis*, shell thickness was thinner (1.57 mm) and shoot length was longer (22.37 cm) compared to the other treatments. On the other hand, the combined treatment ranked the first row in relation to nut (11.83 g) and kernel (5.54 g) weight and shrinkage ratio (10.83%). In addition, the highest yield per tree with 30.67 kg was obtained from this treatment. In conclusion, it is recommended to encourage and expand the use of beneficial microorganisms used as biological fertilizers in walnut cultivation because they have positive effects on many characteristics of horticultural crops through their direct and indirect effects.

Keywords: *Juglans regia*, bacteria, foliar application, quality, yield

INTRODUCTION

The population growth rate, the acceleration of industry and the decrease in production areas as a result of intensive urbanization make it compulsory to obtain high yields from unit area in meeting food needs. In this context, fertilization in crop production is one of the most important cultural practices that positively affect yield and quality. Growth and productivity in plants depend on adequate intake of nutrients [1]. As it is known, the positive effect of fertilization based on climate, soil structure and pH, and occurs with the appropriate time, dose and method in line with the plant's requirements.

On the other hand, the unconscious use of chemical substances that increase yield and quality causes a decrease in soil fertility, as well as adversely affecting human and environmental health and causing economic losses [2]. Unfortunately, along with the deterioration of the natural balance, the amount of beneficial organisms in the soil also decreases, and therefore, the barrenness of the land is revealed [3]. For this purpose, attention should be paid to the protection and sustainability of soils. In this context, the necessity of using inputs that are friendly to human and nature is emphasized for the protection of ecological balance [4].

Farmyard manure is used both to increase the organic matter content and to overcome nutrient deficiencies in the soil. Although this fertilizer is relatively low cost, the difficulty of application, especially in large production areas, limits its use. In addition, due to problems in supply and demand, producers have turned to alternative sources. Awareness of the negative effects of these fertilizers has led to the widespread use of organic-based alternative fertilizers [5].

The final product, which is the output of crop production, is directly related to nutrition and has an impact on health. Due to the increasing awareness of the society on healthy nutrition, the demands for products grown with organic and good agricultural practices and inputs that can be used in these production systems are also increasing. On the other hand, the demand for higher quality and healthier foods is increasing in developed and developing countries [6]. These approaches attract attention for the economic use of natural resources in crop production, sustainability and access to clean products.

Beneficial microorganisms have been used for many years in biotechnology, genetic engineering, human, environmental and food safety [7]. In this sense, nowadays, beneficial microorganisms, especially bacteria, are widely used in agriculture as plant growth promoters. This has led to a reduction in the use of pesticides and chemical fertilizers, thus increasing crop yields and providing better quality products [8, 9]. These bacteria, known as biological agents and microbial fertilizers, are among the solution alternatives in terms of plant development, quality and input reduction with their use in agriculture.

It is reported that the active substances produced by these microorganisms increase the access of plants to nutrients by converting nutrients in soils into a form that plants can use [10, 11]. However, these bacteria are known to have different mechanisms to support plant development such as phytohormone biosynthesis, mechanisms to reduce or prevent environmental stresses, and prevention of plant diseases caused by pathogens [12].

In fruit species, it has been determined to have a positive effect on vegetative development, fruit characteristics, nutrient content, disease control and yield [13, 14]. These applications, which achieve results in a short time and have a direct effect on the amount of product, are applied to soil, leaves and flowers as individually or combination [10, 15]. Although it is stated that plant growth promoting microorganisms are mostly effective in nitrogen and phosphorus uptake, it is known that they also increase the uptake of other elements [10]. In addition, it is predicted that they may be a solution to minimize the damage to plants under stress [11, 14, 16].

Trade, production and consumption balances vary rapidly due to population growth. Changing consumption habits of people, global problems such as hunger and poverty, climate change, food safety issues increase the importance of agriculture [17]. The demand for the consumption of walnuts, which are among the snack dry products, is following a rising trend thanks to the growing awareness of healthy living in the society. It has an important place in health nutrition programs due to its mineral substances, vitamins, antioxidants and unsaturated fatty acids.

Walnut is a product of significant economic value worldwide, which has a wide range of uses in cosmetics and many industries as well as its valuable nutritional content. In Türkiye, which is among the leading producer countries in the world, new orchards have been established especially with the "Chandler" variety and it is noteworthy that the production areas have increased. In the light of these explanations, the aim of this study was to determine the effects of *Bacillus subtilis* bacteria and combined other bacterial species (*Pantoea agglomerans*, *Paenibacillus polymyxa*, *Bacillus megaterium*, *Bacillus megaterium*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*) on nut characteristics, yield and shoot length in "Chandler" walnut variety in Saruhanlı/Manisa.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the research, 12-year-old "Chandler" walnut variety grafted onto seedling rootstock was used as plant material in the producer's orchard in Saruhanlı/Manisa location. This variety, which shows medium growth, has a chilling requirement of 700 hours and blooms in the late season. The fruits that ripen in the middle season have a light kernel color and the shell is easily

broken [18]. In addition to cultural practices and regular irrigation in the orchard, soil fertilizer was applied during the winter rest period and foliar nitrogen, zinc and boron applications were made during the blooming period. Monthly max, min and average temperature values for the year 2023 are given in Table 1 and soil analysis results are located in Table 2.

Table 1. Monthly temperature values (°C)

Months	Max	Min	Avg.
December	22.5	5.2	10.1
January	21.9	2.4	7.5
February	24.7	0.9	7.1
March	25.0	6.0	12.0
April	26.9	7.8	14.7
May	35.1	12.3	19.3
June	37.9	16.6	24.7
July	43.6	18.7	29.2
August	43.3	20.2	29.0
September	38.9	15.5	24.7
October	31.7	9.9	18.8
November	23.4	6.5	15.5

Table 2. Soil analysis results at two depths (0-30 cm and 30-60 cm)

Soil parameters	0-30 cm		30-60 cm	
pH	7.74	Alkaline	7.85	Alkaline
EC (%)	0.046	Salt-free	0.047	Salt-free
CaCO ₃ (%)	9.98	Medium	10.77	Medium
Organic Matter (%)	0.68	Insufficient	0.14	Insufficient
Sand (%)	44.24		44.24	
Clay (%)	30.00		30.00	
Silt (%)	25.76		25.76	
Texture	Loamy soil		Loamy soil	

In the experiment, organic preparations were applied to the trees in two different dates, in May and June, after fruit set. These applications were carried out by foliar spraying as 500 cc/100 L. Microbial fertilizer was applied as a single application containing *Bacillus subtilis* soil-derived beneficial bacteria, which has the ability to produce organic acids and amino acids. By converting the free nitrogen of the air into nitrate and ammonium forms that plants can use, it increases the usefulness of other plant nutrients in the soil and provides good vegetative growth. Accordingly, it causes an increase in yield and product quality [19]. The other microbial fertilizer is a combined fertilizer which contains a large number of live microorganisms such as *Pantoea agglomerans*, *Paenibacillus polymyxa*, *Bacillus megaterium*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens* [20]. In the experiment, in addition to the preparations containing single and combined bacteria, the control group trees were sprayed with water.

At the harvest date (08.10.2023), 30 nut samples from each replicate were separated from the peel and dried in the shade. Analyses were carried out at Ege University, Faculty of Agriculture, Department of Horticulture. Average nut and kernel weight were determined with a precision balance (0.01 g) and expressed in grams. Walnut width (width, cheek diameter), length (length), height (thickness, suture diameter) and shell thickness were measured in millimeters (mm) with a digital caliper. The color of the kernel was detected with a digital colorimeter (CR-400, Minolta Co, Japan) and expressed as L, a, b values. Chroma ($C^* = [a^*2 + b^*2]^{1/2}$) and hue angle ($h^\circ = \tan^{-1} [b^*/a^*]$) values were calculated from the a* and b* values [21]. Yield was recorded in kg tree⁻¹, kernel and shrinkage ratio were found out as %. After

vegetative growth was completed, shoot length was measured on 10 shoots from each tree using a tape measure (cm).

The experiment was planned according to randomized block design with 3 replicates and 3 trees in each replicate. In each replicate, 10 nut samples were evaluated. Analysis of variance was performed using SPSS 20 statistical program. Differences between means were determined by Duncan test ($P \leq 0.05$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In "Chandler" walnut variety, single and combined bacterial applications showed statistical difference in terms of nut and kernel weight, shell thickness, kernel shrinkage, shoot length and yield compared to the control group (Table 3). According to this, while the lowest value for nut weight was measured in the control group (9.81 g), it was determined that the treatments had a positive effect on this trait and nut weight increased to 11.83 g and 11.42 g as a result of combined and single treatments, respectively. Similar situation was also observed in kernel weight. Thus, control (4.42 g) and combined (5.54 g) treatments constituted the limit values. The thickest shell was measured in the control treatment with 1.84 mm, while the thinnest shell was obtained from the single bacteria treatment with 1.57 mm. The treatments had a decreasing effect on shell thickness. Similar result was also obtained in kernel shrinkage. Accordingly, the lowest rate was recorded from combined bacteria treatment (10.83%), followed by single bacteria treatment with 13.33% and control treatment with 20.00%. In shoot length, single (22.37 cm) and combined (19.80 cm) treatments showed an increase compared to control (15.58 cm). Moreover, the highest yield was found out from the combined bacteria treatment with 30.67 kg tree⁻¹, followed by the single bacteria treatment with 24.00 kg tree⁻¹. The lowest yield was measured from untreated trees (20.83 kg tree⁻¹). On the other hand, bacterial treatments on kernel shrinkage and nut size were not statistically significant.

Fruit color parameters measured according to the treatments are shown in Table 4. It was determined that the treatments were not statistically effective on color values. No positive change was measured on kernel color parameters with bacteria treatments.

Table 3. Some nut characteristics, shoot length and yield values according to treatments

Application	Nut weight (g)	Kernel weight (g)	Kernel ratio (%)	Shell thickness (mm)	Nut width (mm)	Nut length (mm)	Nut height (mm)	Shrinkage ratio (%)	Shoot length (cm)	Yield (kg tree ⁻¹)
Control	9.81 b	4.42 b	45.07 ^{ns}	1.84 c	31.50 ^{ns}	31.93 ^{ns}	38.38 ^{ns}	20.00 b	15.58 b	20.83 b
Single	11.42 ab	4.50 b	39.55	1.57 a	31.23	31.50	37.44	13.33 ab	22.37 a	24.00 b
Combined	11.83 a	5.54 a	46.96	1.68 b	31.63	31.99	38.42	10.83 a	19.80 ab	30.67 a

The differences in the means were determined by the Duncan test according to $P \leq 0.05$. ns: Not significant

Table 4. Nut color parameters according to treatments

Application	L*	a*	b*	C*	h ⁰
Control	55.63 ^{ns}	7.26 ^{ns}	29.79 ^{ns}	30.66 ^{ns}	76.31 ^{ns}
Single	54.82	7.16	29.01	29.88	76.14
Combined	54.79	7.26	28.88	29.78	75.87

The differences in the means were determined by the Duncan test according to $P \leq 0.05$. ns: Not significant

Beneficial bacteria that transform nutrients into usable form have positive effects on pomological characteristics, shoot length and yield in fruit species such as strawberry, apricot,

walnut and raspberry [22-25]. In a study emphasizing the reduction in the use of chemical inputs with bacteria applications in quince, it was stated that an increase in fruit weight and yield was achieved with the use of bacteria and half dose fertilizer [26]. However, it is expressed that this effect varies depending on plant species, bacterial isolate, application method and temperature [27]. In another study conducted in olives with commercial microbial fertilizer application, it was reported that a statistical increase was recorded in terms of fruit and kernel weight compared to the control [28]. A similar situation was observed in our study and an increase in nut and kernel weight and yield was recorded. In fact, the effect was even higher in the combined treatment in which different bacteria were used together.

As it is known, fruit quality traits, shoot length and yield vary according to years and locations. Therefore, the effects of genotype, environment and interactions on fruit and internal quality traits are mentioned [29]. In a study conducted on the same walnut cultivar, it was reported that due to the low summer temperatures at the high altitude location in Manisa province, the kernel weight of the nut could not be filled completely. It was explained that this situation led to relatively low fruit weight in the control group trees that were not treated with commercial bacteria [24]. In our study conducted in Saruhanlı location, which is close to the sea level, it was determined that the treatments had a positive effect on nut and kernel weight and shrinkage ratio due to the effect of temperature and these temperatures allowing bacteria to function.

On the other hand, the fact that fruit set is higher than standard productive trees can affect fruit quality at harvest time, especially causing a decrease in fruit weight and size. It is known that crop load has an effect on pomological characteristics. Therefore, there may be a negative correlation between yield and fruit size and weight [30]. In this study conducted by us in Saruhanlı district, it was determined that especially nut width, length and height decreased relatively in the treatments with high yield and were not statistically effective. In addition, the lack of change in color parameters with bacteria treatments is similar to the findings of Atılgan et al. [10] in Salihli cherry variety. Similarly, it is stated that plant growth promoting rhizobacteria application had no effect on fruit color values in Eşme quince variety [26].

For shoot length, in another study conducted in Manisa province with the same walnut variety, a partial increase was recorded with bacterial treatments [24]. However, it is stated that a statistical increase was recorded in hazelnut, another nut species [31]. A similar situation occurred in this study and *Bacillus* bacteria were prominent. This positive effect of bacteria on vegetative development may be a result of the change in hormone levels [32]. Because, cytokinin promotes plant growth, while auxin increases root area and contributes to water and nutrient uptake. These effects of bacteria contribute positively to vegetative development in plants. In addition to the positive change in hormone levels with beneficial bacteria, yield and quality increase can be observed through mechanisms such as nitrogen fixation and phosphorus solubilization [25].

CONCLUSION

Plant nutrient deficiency in our soils reveals the importance of plant nutrition practices during the production period. In nut species such as walnut, kernel quality is important and preferred by consumers. On the other hand, in recent years, microorganisms have been widely used in fruit growing thanks to their direct and indirect effects. In this context, as a result of bacterial treatments in "Chandler" walnut cultivar, it was determined that the traits examined, except fruit size and color parameters, improved positively. The combined treatment ranked first especially in nut and kernel weight, shrinkage ratio and yield values. With the single treatment containing only *Bacillus subtilis*, the thinnest shell was obtained and shoot lengths were longer. Especially in terms of yield, an increase of 50% with the combined bacteria

treatment is noteworthy. Beneficial microorganisms, which are important for human and environmental health, are recommended to be widely used in walnut cultivation due to their positive effects such as increasing quality and yield as well as reducing input use. In addition, the widespread use of these environmentally friendly practices is also important in terms of protecting the natural balance. On the other hand, it is thought that it would be useful to continue studies to determine the effects of combined, foliar and soil applications in terms of biological control and cultivation of diseases and pests that are problematic in walnut.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Zaman, M., Kurepin, L., Catto, W., Pharis, R. (2014): Enhancing crop yield with the use of N-based fertilizers co-applied with plant hormones or growth regulators. Published on line in Wiley On line Library.
- [2] Demirtaş, I., Arı, N., Arpacıoğlu, A., Kaya, H., Özkan, C. (2005): Değişik organik kökenli gübrelerin kimyasal özellikleri. *Derim* 22(2):47-52.
- [3] Sinha, R.K., Herat, S. (2009): The concept of sustainable agriculture: an issue of food safety and security for people, economic prosperity for the farmers and ecological security for the nations. *50(2):129-134 (2021) 134 American-Eurasian J. Agric. & Environ. Sci. 5(S):1-55.*
- [4] Bellitürk, K. (2016): Sürdürülebilir tarımsal üretimde katı atık yönetimi için vermikompost teknolojisi. *Çukurova Tarım Gıda Bilimleri Dergisi* 31(3):1-5.
- [5] Aydın Can, B., Ünal, M., Can, O. (2019): Farklı yarıya gübresi uygulamalarının marul yetiştiriciliğinde verim ve kalite üzerine etkileri. *Uluslararası Tarım ve Yaban Hayatı Bilimleri Dergisi (UTYHBD)*, 5(1):18-24. Doi: 10.24180/ijaws.481660
- [6] Ak, B.E., Parlakçı, H. (2018): Fruit set, yield and some quality traits of different foreign almond cultivars grown Şanlıurfa province. *Proceedings of the 9. International Agricultural Symposium Agrosym.*
- [7] Higa, T., Parr, J.F. (1994): Beneficial Effective Microorganisms for a Sustainable Agriculture Environment. *International Nature Farming Research Center Atami Japan 25s.*
- [8] Flores-Felix, J.D., Silva, L.R., Rivera, L.P., Marcos-Garcia, M., Garcia-Fraile, P., Martinez-Molina, E., Mateos, P.F., Velazquez, E., Andrade, P., Rivas, R. (2015): Plants probiotics as a tool to produce highly functional fruits: the case of *Phyllobacterium* and vitamin C in strawberries. *PLoS One* 10: p. 1-101.
- [9] Küçük, C. (2019): Bitki Probiyotik Bakteriler: Bitkiler Üzerindeki Roller ve Uygulamalar. *International Journal of Life Sciences and Biotechnology* 2(1): p. 1-15.
- [10] Atılğan, H., Mısırlı, A. Özaktan, H. Şen, F., Acarsoy Bilgin, N. (2019): Bakteri ve kompost çayı uygulamalarının Salihli kiraz çeşidinde meyve özellikleri, verim ve besin elementi içeriklerine etkileri. *Ege Üniv. Ziraat Fak. Derg.* 56(4):409-416.
- [11] Şelem, E., Nohutçu, L., Tunçtürk, R., Tunçtürk, M. (2021): Bitki Gelişimini Teşvik Eden Bakteri Uygulamalarının Kuraklık Stresi Koşullarında Yetiştirilen Aynısafa (*Calendula officinalis* L.) Bitkisinin Bazı Büyüme Parametreleri ile Fizyolojik Özellikleri Üzerine Etkisi. *YYÜ TAR BİL DERG (YYU J AGR SCI)* 31(4):886-897.
- [12] Malua, E., Vassilev, N. (2014): A contribution to set a legal framework for biofertilisers. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* 98: p. 6599–6607.
- [13] Shakeel, S., Hassan, D.G. (2018): In vitro bioefficacy of rhizobacteria, isolated from walnut (*Juglans regia* L.) Rhizosphere in North-Western Himalayas, against Five Fungal Phytopathogens. *Applied Biological Research Volume* 20(3):234-243. 10.5958/0974-4517.2018.00032.0
- [14] Wang, L., Zhu, T. (2023): Strong Opponent of Walnut Anthracnose—*Bacillus velezensis* and Its Transcriptome Analysis. *Microorganisms* 11, 1885. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms11081885>

- [15] Acarsoy Bilgin, A., Yağmur, B., Özaktan, H., Akbaba, M. (2023): Effects of Foliar Application of Nutrients and Beneficial Bacteria on Fruit Properties and Nutrient Concentrations of 'Chandler' Walnut Variety. *Erwerbs-Obstbau* 65 p.567–578. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10341-023-00867-y>
- [16] Lotf, N., Soleimani, A., Çakmakçı, R., Vahdati, K., Mohammadi, P. (2022): Characterization of plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) in Persian walnut associated with drought stress tolerance. *Natureportolio* 12:12725. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-16852-6>
- [17] Ardıç, M., Yürüksoy, H. (2021): Bazı doğal gübrelerin Porsuk baraj göleti iklim koşulları altında ceviz gelişimi ve yetiştiriciliği üzerine etkileri. *Research Journal of Biology Sciences E-ISSN: 1308-0262* 14(2): 156-169.
- [18] Özçağırın, R., Ünal, A. Özeker, E. ve İsfendiyaroğlu, M. (2014): Ilıman İklim Meyve Türleri, Sert Kabuklu Meyveler Cilt III, Ege Üniversitesi Ziraat Fakültesi Yayınları, No: 566.
- [19] Anonim (2023a): <https://supersol.com.tr/urunler/ss-stomafix/>
- [20] Anonim (2023b): <https://supersol.com.tr/urunler/ss-super-pan-2/>
- [21] Mcguire, R.G. (1992): Reporting of Objective Color Measurements. *Hortscience* 27:1254-1255.
- [22] Ağgün, Z., Geçer, M.K., Aslantaş, R. (2018): Bazı Çilek Çeşitlerinde Kök Bakterisi Uygulamalarının Meyve Verimi ve Verim Özellikleri Üzerine Etkileri. *Uluslararası Tarım ve Yaban Hayatı Bilimleri Dergisi (UTYHBD)*, 4(1): 20 – 25. doi: 10.24180/ijaws.418523
- [23] Eşitken, A., Karlıdag, H. Ercisli, S. Turan, M. ve Şahin, F. (2003): The effects of spraying a growth promoting bacterium on the yield, growth and nutrient element composition of leaves of apricot (*Prunus armeniaca* L. cv. Hacihaliloglu). *Aust. J. Agric. Res.* 54, 377– 380.
- [24] Acarsoy Bilgin, N., Mısırlı, A., Şen, F. (2020): Cevizde (cv. Chandler) Kompoze Mikrobiyal Gübre Kullanımının Verim ve Kalite Parametreleri Üzerine Etkilerinin Araştırılması. *Ziraat Mühendiliği* (370), 84-93 DOI: 10.33724/zm.731026
- [25] İpek, M., Arıkan, Ş., Eşitken, A., Pırlak, L. (2018): Bitki Gelişimini Artırıcı Rizobakterilerin "Heritage" Ahududu (*Rubus idaeus* L.) Çeşidinde Bitki Gelişimi, Verim ve Meyve Kalitesi Üzerine Etkisi. *YYÜ TAR BİL DERG (YYU J AGR SCI)* 28(1): 42-48.
- [26] Gerçekçioğlu, R., Ertürk, A., Öz Atasever, Ö. (2018): Bitki Büyümesini Teşvik Edici Rizobakteri (PGPR) Uygulamasının Eşme Ayva Çeşidinde (*Cydonia vulgaris* L.) Verim ve Meyve Özellikleri Üzerine Etkileri. *Gaziosmanpaşa Üniversitesi Ziraat Fakültesi Dergisi.* 35 (3), 209-216.
- [27] Egamberdiyeva, D., Höflich, G. (2003): Influence of growthpromoting bacteria on the growth of wheat in different soils and temperatures. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry* 35, 973-978.
- [28] Acarsoy Bilgin, N. (2019): Yaprakdan Gübre Uygulamalarının Gemlik Zeytin Çeşidinde Verim ve Kalite Üzerine Etkileri. *International Aegean Symposium on Innovative Interdisciplinary Scientific Researches.* 449- 453.
- [29] Mertoğlu, K., Evrenosoğlu, Y. (2017): Ateş Yanıklığı (*Erwinia amylovora*) Hastalığına Dayanıklılık İslahında, Hastalığa Karşı Testlenmiş F1 Melez Armut Popülasyonunun Fenolojik ve Meyve Özellikleri. *Tekirdağ Ziraat Fakültesi Dergisi.* 14 (03): 104-115.
- [30] Treder, W. (2008): Relationship between yield, crop density coefficient and average fruit weight of „Gala“ apple. *Journal of Fruit and Ornamental Plant Research*, 16:53-63.
- [31] Rostamikia, Y., Tabari, M., Asgharzadeh, A., Rahmani, A. (2016): Effect of Plant Growth Promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPR) and Cold Stratification on Seed Germination and Early Growth of *Corylus avellana* L. *Austrian Journal of Forest Science.* 4: 337-352.
- [32] İpek, M., Pırlak, L., Eşitken, A., Dönmez, M.F., Turan, M., Şahin, F. (2014): Plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) increase yield, growth and nutrition of strawberry under high calcareous soil conditions. *Journal of Plant Nutrition*, 37:990– 1001.